

DEVELOPMENT OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLE COMPETENCIES AND MEDICAL LITERACY IN ADOLESCENTS

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the main methods of creating a healthy lifestyle. The relevance of developing new methods of promoting healthy principles and habits is stressed. The method of interaction between students and teenagers in the framework of the project "Healthy Conversation" is presented.

Introduction

Due to the predominance of depopulation and the general trend towards population aging in the Republic of Belarus, there is a growing need to strengthen, maintain and restore the health of the population. According to the World Health Organization, by providing an optimal environment and a healthy lifestyle, at least 50% of existing diseases can be avoided. At the same time, prevention is not only better than treatment - it requires less economic costs [1]. A healthy lifestyle is a lifestyle that helps to significantly reduce the risk of serious illness or premature death, as well as improve the quality of human life. The main components of a healthy lifestyle are: valeological literacy; balanced diet; optimal motor mode, taking into account age, gender and physiological characteristics of the body; observance of the daily regimen and the optimal alternation of work and rest; favorable ecological and hygienic conditions; rejection of bad habits; prevention of psycho-emotional distress and stress; safe sexual behavior; compliance with the rules of personal and public hygiene; reasonable use of the health-improving effects of environmental factors; medical activity and dynamic health monitoring, self-help skills and self-monitoring of health status; positive environmental behavior.

Main part

In the process of forming a healthy lifestyle (HLLS), the priority target audience is children and adolescents. In the Republic of Belarus, a system of healthy lifestyles for the population has been developed, which unites the multilateral, intersectoral activities of a wide social network. State educational standards, schools, specialized institutions promote health by following the following stages: informational, psychological, reproductive or practical, experience or acquisition of skills, habitual way of life. There are some methods of hygienic training and education:

1. Information-receptive - the transfer of ready-made information on the preservation and promotion of health by a specialist to

trained persons who assimilate it at the level of conscious perception and memorization.

2. Reproductive - in the organization by a specialist, the reproduction of existing knowledge by students in the framework of theoretical and practical classes.

3. The method of problematic presentation of information - setting scientific and cognitive practical tasks by a specialist in front of students, in revealing the logic of their solution.

4. Heuristic method - setting scientific, cognitive and practical tasks for students, revealing the logic of searching for their solutions, as well as organizing independent setting and solving problems by students [4].

However, according to statistics, the number of completely healthy school teams does not exceed 15% on average and decreases to 7% in the senior classes, where the proportion of students with health problems, including those with chronic pathology, is noticeably increasing, which is a negative trend for pediatric service [3].

In order to form medical literacy and a responsible attitude to health, the Healthy Conversation project has been operating at the Grodno State Medical University on the basis of the pediatric faculty since October 2021.

The subject of the project is the organization of events aimed at developing the competencies of a healthy lifestyle and medical literacy among students of institutions of general secondary education. Project implementation methods:

- search for information, study and analysis of sources used in preparation for events;
- use of multimedia presentations, booklets, information booklets or posters;
- survey in a test form, questionnaires to control the effectiveness of the meetings.

Communication on problematic issues is organized in a trusting atmosphere aimed at developing healthy lifestyle competencies in adolescents. The information used is covered in an accessible form and is relevant, evidence-based and practice-oriented. The main target groups are students of grades VIII-XI of EE "Gymnasium No. 10", EE "Secondary School No. 23", EE "Secondary School No. 37".

Project objectives:

- Reveal the actual problems of formation of healthy lifestyle competencies among students;
- Contribute to the prevention of students' addictive behavior (smoking, early alcohol abuse, risky sexual behavior, drug addiction, etc.);
- To help students develop the competence of a healthy lifestyle and medical literacy necessary to provide first aid to the victim and to themselves;
- Increase students' awareness of disease prevention and increase the body's resistance to environmental factors;
- Contribute to the promotion of a healthy lifestyle as a priority direction of state policy.

To assess the functioning of the project through testing and questionnaires conducted at events with adolescents, a study was conducted that reflects the effectiveness of students' work within the framework of the Healthy Conversation project.

According to the results of an anonymous survey among 40 participants of 8 lectures using a test created in Google form, 100% of students apply the acquired knowledge in everyday life, 100% note the importance of discussing healthy lifestyle topics from a medical perspective, 97.2% - consider this project important. This proves not only the correct choice of methods of communication and presentation of the material, but also the relevance of holding such events.

The interaction of medical university students with students allows to increase the level of trust in medical workers and reduce the negative impact on students of various information sources, which are not always reliable and can distort the concept of the beauty and health of a growing organism, as well as incline to addictive behavior.

Conclusion

Thus, the importance of the Healthy Conversation project is beyond doubt. Determination of the content of significant topics, the transfer of new information from future specialists in the field of medicine to students in the form of informative, exciting interactive lectures and dialogue favors the formation of significant competencies and medical literacy that contribute to the formation of a culture of a healthy lifestyle. This form of student communication contributes to the psychological readiness of schoolchildren to change their usual lifestyle and facilitates the formation of individual and social consciousness. The functioning of the project contributes to the implementation of the main tasks of the national strategy for the preservation of human health: disease prevention, promotion of health.

References:

1. World Health Organization. Thirteenth General Program of Work 2019-2023 // 2018.
2. The state of health of children in the Republic of Belarus [Electronic resource]. - 2022. - Access mode: <http://www.naturalmedics.ru/dots-889-1.html>. - Access date: 03/17/2022.
3. Burkhonova M.X The role of educators in the development of children's abilities and creativity through the use of visual aids in preschool education // Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal 156-158 b
4. Burkhonova M.Kh. "Effectiveness of forming creativity in preschool children based on visual arts", 000 "Open science" Science and Education, 2022 910-914-p
5. Vygotsky L.S. Pedagogical psychology. Pod ed. V. V. Davydova. M.: Pedagogy, 1991. 480 p.
6. Курбонова Г. Н. Формирование профессионального мышления у будущих медиков-педагогов // Освіта та розвиток обдарованої особистості. – 2019. – № 3. – С. 25-29.
7. Kurbanova G.N. The role of innovative lectures in the improvement of students professional thinking // ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 2021, Vol. 11, Issue 3, March, DOI: 10.5958/2249-7137.2021.00419.5. P.-2360-2369.
8. Курбанова Гулноз Негматовна ТАЛАБАЛАР КАСБИЙ ТАФАККУРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ЗАМОНАВИЙ МАЪРУЗА МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ // Биология и интегративная медицина. 2021. №2 (49). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/talabalar-kasbiy-tafakkurini-rivozhlantirishda-zamonaviy-maruzamash-ulotlarining-a-amiyati>
9. Курбанова Г.Н. Пути повышения эффективности обучения русскому языку студентов-медиков с использованием интерактивных технологий на занятиях по русскому языку // Вестник Таджикского национального университета 2019 №5. С -207-212.
10. KURBANOVA G.N. PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION'S ROLE AND IMPORTANCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL THINKING. // EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH. - 2022/10/19. - №2 (11). - pp. 914-925.
11. Kurbanova , G. (2022). PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT VOSITASIDA KASBIY TAFAKKURNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IJTIMOYIY-TARIXIY ASOSLARI. Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences,

Philosophy and Culture, 2(9), 12–16. извлечено от <https://www.in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/3614>

12. Г.Н. Қурбонова Бўлажак ўқитувчиларда касбий-оператив тафаккурини ривожлантиришнинг дидактик имкониятлари // Таълим ва инновацион тадқиқотлар. - 2022/8/8. - №8(8). - С. 109-115.

13. G.N., K. (2022). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE ANCESTORS HERITAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL THINKING OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS. Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture, 2(2), 272–277. извлечено от <https://www.in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/828>

14. Kurbanova G.N., Musaeva, D. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL THINKING OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. KRS Journal of Social Education, 2(2), 56–61. Retrieved from <https://krsjournal.com/index.php/krsjse/article/view/52>

15. G.N, K. . (2021). Forming professional thinking among future medical pedagogists. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 12, 84-88. Retrieved from <http://cejsr.academicjournal.io/index.php/journal/article/view/518>

